

The Alan Turing Institute

Extending the impact of the TPS
programme, and The Alan Turing
Institute, through **Open Research**

Malvika Sharan

Pronouns: she/her

**The
Alan Turing
Institute**

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Institute**

*Research
Programmes*

The Alan Turing Institute

- The national institute for data science and artificial intelligence
- 10 research programmes

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Turing 2.0 vision

- **Research** of national priorities
- Growing our **communities**
- National leadership to improve **skills**

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*Research
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Tools,
Practices and
Systems

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- The national institute for data science and artificial intelligence
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Tools, Practices and Systems (TPS)

- *Building open source infrastructure to empower a decentralised network of people who connect data with domain experts*

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Tools,
Practices and
Systems

Ensure that research and data-driven AI solutions at the Turing **use and build on open source** “tools, practices and systems” **by empowering people with open research skills**

Open Research

Everyone can **access, reuse, build upon and distribute** openly licensed resources.

Open Communities

Everyone can access, reuse, build upon and distribute openly licensed resources.

Practical framework for collaboration, peer production and project sustainability.

Open Research and community

Process of granting **access to skills**
and support needed to participate

Different goals but **common mission**

Open Research and community

Process of granting access to skills and support needed to participate

Different goals but **common mission**

- 1. Share research outputs publicly*
- 2. Community Collaboration*
- 3. Broaden the skills and diversity*

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*Research
Programmes*

Tools,
Practices and
Systems

Turing
Data
Stories

*building open source
infrastructure that is
accessible to all*

References: <https://www.turing.ac.uk/events/tools-practices-systems-monthly-meet>, <https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/welcome>, <https://alan-turing-institute.github.io/TuringDataStories-fastpages/>, <https://raphtory.github.io/>, <https://acocac.github.io/environmental-ai-book>, <https://www.turing.ac.uk/research/research-projects/digital-twin-worlds-first-3d-printed-stainless-steel-bridge>, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5541486

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**Turing 2.0
Vision**

Tools,
Practices and
Systems

**Coordinated
Efforts**

**Open Research
Outputs**

**Global Open
Infrastructure**

Bidirectional flow of knowledge, resources and evidence

Extending Impact through Open Research

- Establish and lead the team of Community Managers
- Conduct Research with open science and community focus
- Coordinate efforts through TPS to grow data and research communities
- Lead skills and capacity building efforts through strategic partnerships

Team of Community Managers

- Strategic implementation and **scaling of TPS efforts**
- **Budget and funding** for the team and TPS
- **Embedding Open**, reproducible and Interoperable practices across the Turing research

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EMBL Bio-IT

 EMBO
excellence in
life sciences

CS&S Code for
Science &
Society

Conducting Open Research

*Open and community-led
Guides to data science*

>2.5 years, 5 guides, 180 subchapters

- Guidance, training, case studies etc.
- 285 GitHub contributors, 3000+ monthly visitors, 2300+ followers
- Scoping, delivery and reporting on community-oriented research
- Cited by 30+ peer-reviewed articles, policies, reports, training, projects

5,501
views

6,686
downloads

Conducting Open Research

- **Governance and sustainability** for open and reproducible research
- Research-based **improvement of digital accessibility**
- Context-based **testing and uptake of data science skills** (collaboration with RAMs)

*Open and community-led
Guides to data science*

Coordinating Efforts

- Applying **open approaches** to training and capacity building.
- **Interconnecting** teams, resources and knowledge

Coordinating Efforts

- **Connect and align** visions and goals
- **Open up resources** across groups
- Through shared activities, create **quantitative and qualitative impact**

The de.NBI/ELIXIR-DE training platform - Bioinformatics training in Germany and across Europe within ELIXIR. F1000Research, 8.
<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.20244.2>

Lead Skills and Capacity Building Efforts

- **Leading projects** on skill building through TPS
- Community manager team will **scale efforts**
- Cross-pollination with **external open research initiatives**
- Establishing **metrics and pathways** for feedback
- Collecting **evidence and reporting** on impact
- Notable **investment into the global** open infrastructure

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Advocating for open, reproducible and inclusive Research

Within The Alan Turing Institute

- National Skills & Strategy team
- Academic Engagement Team
- Turing-Crick Data Training
- Research Engineering Group
- Research Applications Team
- Data Study Group

International Communities

- Software Sustainability Institute
- The Carpentries
- Open Life Science
- Code for Science & Society
- International Society of RSE
- Jupyter Strategic Community

Logos taken from respective websites.

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